

Using 'Trivial' Python modules

We are a group of researchers from Concordia University studying the impact of reusing trivial Python modules in the PyPI (The Python Package Index) package management ecosystem. We are conducting a quick survey (5 min.) to better understand how developers use trivial Python modules.

A 'trivial' module can be thought of as a "code that can be quickly/easily written instead of imported", i.e., a function for checking if two strings are equal.

Please notice that your participation in the study is completely voluntary, and your answers will not be linked to you in anyway. This survey is a part of academic research and it is not related or sponsored by any industrial partner. Your participation will help both software researchers and developers to advance the general understanding of developer practices. We very much appreciate your response to our survey and thank you in advance.

* Required

1. How would you best describe yourself? *

Mark only one oval.

- Developer working in the industry
- Full time developer
- Independent developer
- Casual developer
- Other: _____

2. How many years of development experience do you have? *

Mark only one oval.

- Less than 1 Year
- Between 1 and 3 Years
- Between 3 and 5 Years
- More than 5 Years

A 'trivial' module can be thought of as a "code that can be quickly/easily written instead of imported", i.e., a function for checking if two strings are equal.

3. How many 'trivial' modules do you generally use in your project(s)? *

Mark only one oval.

0 - 2

3 - 6

7 - 10

11 - 15

16 - 20

21+

4. Do you think adding a dependency (an extra module) for a task that is 'trivial', such as checking if two strings are equal, is a bad thing? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Other: _____

5. In your opinion, what are the **ADVANTAGES** of using these 'trivial' modules versus writing the code yourself? *

6. In your opinion, what are the DISADVANTAGES of using these 'trivial' modules versus writing the code yourself? *

7. If you wish to receive the results of our research, please enter your email here:

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